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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARISSA PELONIA BAÑEZ

TEACHER III

Basilio B Chan Memorial Agricultural Industrial School

Lavezares District I, Division of Northern Samar

marissapbanez@gmail.com

“LIFE’S CHOICE TO TAKE”

Life is plain, breathe
Keeping alive is as intricate as the veins that thrive,
Heap of choices, take but one
Consequences follow, could never be undone

Do what is right,
A noble stand comes with a weighty might
In the quest for what’s right, serenity departs
The realms of dreams, a life apart

Do what is good,
In God’s light, stand for truth
With heart upright, and spirit bright,
What prize awaits the righteous, a home in the afterlife

Heed! A calm mind, a gentle deed,
A peaceful life, a quiet soul, is what we all need.